

Assessing the competitiveness and trade-offs of national hydrogen strategies in the Maghreb: TIMES scenario-based analysis

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Ibrahim Dincer

Keywords:

Energy system modelling
North Africa
Green hydrogen
Decarbonization
Renewable electricity

ABSTRACT

North Africa's Maghreb countries Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria aim to become key players in the global green hydrogen market. However, rising hydrogen demand challenges their ability to balance domestic, decarbonization efforts with export ambitions. This study assesses the techno-economic trade-offs between national hydrogen targets and export goals, evaluating their alignment with climate commitments using the TIMES-MAGe model. Five scenarios explore variations in electrolysis energy sourcing (renewables vs. grid) and water supply (surface vs. desalinated), under both local-only and export-oriented strategies. Results show that while export-driven hydrogen production is feasible, it imposes significant economic and resource burdens. By 2050, exports sharply increase hydrogen production costs, electricity prices, investment needs, and water use. The competitiveness of renewable electricity is weakened as most renewable electricity is allocated to hydrogen exports, constraining domestic decarbonization. Intra-regional hydrogen trade is less cost-effective than domestic supply, with pipeline repurposing offering the most viable trade option. The findings inform future policy for cost-effective hydrogen development.

List of abbreviations including units and nomenclature

ALK	Alkaline Electrolysis	MENA –	Middle East and North Africa
CAPEX	Capital expenditure	MESSAGE-SPLAT	Model for energy supply strategy alternatives and their general environmental impact – System planning and analysis tool
CCS	Carbon capture and storage	NDCs	Nationally determined contributions
CSP	Concentrated solar power	NHS	National hydrogen strategies
DZA	Algeria	OPEX	Operational expenditure
EDGAR	Emissions database for global atmospheric research	OSeMOSYS	Open-source energy modelling system
EU	European union	PEM	Proton exchange membrane electrolysis

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GDP	Gross domestic product	PtX	Power-to-X
GHG	Greenhouse gas	PV	Photovoltaic
H₂	Hydrogen	RE	Renewable energy
IEA	International energy agency	REPowerEU	Renewable energy plan of the European union
IRENA	International renewable energy agency	RES-E	Renewable electricity
LEAP	Long-range energy alternatives planning system	SMR	Steam methane reforming
LT-LEDS	Long-term low emission development strategies	SOEC	Solid oxide electrolysis cell
MAR	Morocco	SWRO	Seawater reverse osmosis
MARKAL-EFOM	MARKet ALlocation – Energy flow optimization model	TUN	Tunisia

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This article is part of a special issue entitled: Hydrogen Production and Transportation (Pfeifer) published in International Journal of Hydrogen Energy.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.150193>

Received 23 March 2025; Received in revised form 2 June 2025; Accepted 25 June 2025

Available online 30 June 2025

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MedHySol	Mediterranean hydrogen and solar project
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1. Introduction

The urgent need to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and mitigate climate change is accelerating the global shift to sustainable energy [1]. Hydrogen, the universe's most abundant element, is emerging as a pivotal energy carrier because it integrates with existing infrastructure and offers higher energy density than conventional fuels. [1]. Notably, the combustion of 1 kg of hydrogen generates almost four times the energy produced by an equivalent amount of gasoline [2].

Hydrogen is already a key player in the industrial sector; however, its production remains largely dependent on fossil fuels. As of 2023, an estimated 95 % of global hydrogen output was derived from fossil-based sources [3]. Given net-zero goals, producing low-carbon hydrogen has become a focal point for researchers and policymakers. Low-carbon hydrogen is seen as a key emissions-reduction tool for sectors that now rely on fossil-derived hydrogen (e.g., ammonia production, refining) and for replacing conventional fuels in other hard-to-abate industries [4], namely iron and steel, and long-distance transportation.

The classification of low-carbon hydrogen is based on its production method and the level of associated GHG emissions. Grey hydrogen is produced via steam-methane reforming of natural gas, releasing substantial CO₂. Blue hydrogen uses the same process but adds carbon capture and storage. Green hydrogen is generated by renewable-powered electrolysis, yielding near-zero emissions [5]. Governments are leveraging renewables to produce low-cost electricity and green hydrogen, advancing a sustainable energy future [6,7].

Many countries have entered the race for green hydrogen, often referred to as the “energy of the future” [8]. According to the IEA's September 2024 update, 41 governments, responsible for roughly 80 % of global energy-related CO₂ emissions, now have national hydrogen strategies, with North African countries among them [9–11]. Paired with the EU's REPowerEU goal (2022) of importing 10 Mt yr⁻¹ of green hydrogen by 2030, North Africa's rich renewable resources and existing gas-pipeline links make it a leading candidate to supply this demand [12]. North African governments recognize hydrogen's strategic value for energy security and climate action, elevating it to a cornerstone of their long-term sustainability. By embedding green hydrogen within national transition plans, they aim to secure leadership in the global market while fulfilling Paris Agreement commitments through their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and Long-Term Low Emission Development Strategies (LT-LEDS) targets.

To support this vision, several North African countries, such as Morocco and Tunisia, have developed National Hydrogen Strategies (NHS) aiming to leverage their abundant renewable energy resources to develop a low-carbon hydrogen economy [13]. However, most of these NHS are primarily designed for export, framing green hydrogen as a commodity intended to meet European energy needs rather than prioritizing domestic decarbonization [14]. North African's NHS offer limited details on how green hydrogen will be integrated into domestic energy systems, suggesting that local decarbonization may not be the primary focus of these strategies. This export-oriented approach raises pressing concerns about its impact on renewable energy deployment in the region, particularly the risk that infrastructure investments may divert renewable capacity away from national grids, potentially slowing North Africa's decarbonization. Additionally, ensuring that hydrogen production relies on new renewable capacity [15], rather than repurposing existing resources, remains a significant challenge. Without this additionality, overlapping energy infrastructures could strain national electricity systems instead of strengthening them, ultimately impacting

domestic energy security leading to a crucial question: To which extent will large-scale green hydrogen exports in North Africa impact local decarbonization?

2. Literature review

The literature on green hydrogen in North Africa varies in scale, from global reviews [16] and country-level analyses (e.g., Algeria [17]) to regional studies of Europe [18,19] and North Africa [1]. Some works even treat Europe and North Africa as a single unit [20,21], often overlooking the region's internal production and transport challenges.

North of Africa green hydrogen export potential has increasingly captured the attention of several researchers [3], focusing on the economic and regulatory conditions for the trade between the two regions [22], or exploring multiple exports scenarios and its effects. Utilizing the TIAM-ECN energy system model [21] for instance assess future electricity and hydrogen exchanges between Europe and North Africa, highlighting that EU–North Africa hydrogen and electricity trades could generate up to €50 billion yr⁻¹ by 2050. The same model is applied by Timmerberg [23] to evaluate renewable hydrogen production and export to Central Europe by blending it into existing natural gas pipelines. The study indicates that North Africa holds significant potential for low-cost hydrogen production, with estimated outputs in the range of petawatt-hours per year and production costs between €1.5 and €3 per kilogram of hydrogen.

Pinto [24], used the JRC-EU-TIMES model to examine the potential for green hydrogen exports from North Africa to Europe and its contribution to EU decarbonization efforts. The findings confirm that North African green hydrogen exports could supply up to 16.5 % of EU demand by 2050, significantly aiding decarbonization.

At this point, it is worth highlighting the study by Guillot [3], using TIMES-EUNA, explores EU–North Africa hydrogen trade and highlights how RES capacity limits increase North African costs by 21 % and double capacity needs. However, the study omits alignment with national hydrogen strategies, existing infrastructure, and investment costs; simplifies transport routes and ignores their cost implications; and neglects desalination and raw-vs-desalinated water trade-offs, critical factors in the Maghreb.

Despite these valuable contributions, the existing studies have not sufficiently accounted for the unique national contexts, including ambitious renewable targets and other specific factors influencing energy transitions at the country level. While the economic advantages of Euro-North African cooperation in green hydrogen trade are widely acknowledged, critical trade-offs, particularly regarding the expansion of renewable energy within North Africa, remain less explored and only a limited number of studies have taken a holistic approach to examining these complex dynamics.

Among them, it is important to highlight the work of IRENA [25], Utilizing the MESSAGE-SPLAT model, evaluating four distinct scenarios for the development of North Africa's electricity system, considering varying demand levels and hydrogen export potential. What sets this research apart is its country-level modeling, incorporating national electrical interconnections, unlike many studies that generalize Europe and North Africa as two broad regions. Caillard [26] assesses Morocco's Green Hydrogen Roadmap, analyzing the country's capability to achieve its ambitious targets, including green hydrogen exportation through the lens of the energy trilemma using the OSeMOSYS model. The findings suggest that financing green hydrogen at the envisioned scale could place an overwhelming financial strain on the Moroccan government. Consequently, the study advises a reassessment of the roadmap, proposing a delay and a downsizing of its scope. The same case study was examined in Ref. [27], which analyzed Morocco's hydrogen exportation and its interaction with domestic electricity systems, emphasizing sector coupling and temporal hydrogen regulation. However, the study focuses solely on Morocco and does not quantify investment needs, or considers international trade. In contrast, our work goes beyond by adopting a

broader Maghreb scope, covering Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria, and applying a technology-rich TIMES model to explore cost-optimal electricity and hydrogen pathways, explicitly capturing both domestic consumption and regional trade dynamics and investment implications. Additionally, our study introduces a critical environmental dimension in the region by considering water stress under different hydrogen scenarios.

Belhaj [28] investigates Algeria's power sector expansion under different hydrogen export scenarios, energy efficiency measures, and fuel-switching strategies. Employing the Low Emissions Analysis Platform (LEAP), the study examines how hydrogen production could be integrated into Algeria's energy system and its potential impact on decarbonization. The results indicate that achieving a fully renewable electricity system by 2050 remains highly improbable without significant policy reforms, primarily due to Algeria's low natural gas prices. These findings emphasize the necessity of evaluating hydrogen exports alongside domestic decarbonization efforts to fully understand the trade-offs and interactions involved.

Beyond energy-related challenges, hydrogen production may also pose additional risks to water availability in North Africa, a region already experiencing extreme water scarcity, with per capita water resources falling below the critical threshold of 500 m³ per year [29]. Producing 1 kg of green hydrogen through water electrolysis consumes 9 L of water (stoichiometric relation), with some electrolysis manufacturers' reporting even higher values between 10.01–22.40 L per kg of H₂ depending on electrolysis type and technological performance [30]. This represents considerable amount of water for countries already facing severe water stress. Without careful planning, large-scale hydrogen production could intensify competition for limited water resources, potentially impacting agricultural needs, human consumption, and even driving up water costs. Despite its relevance none of the above-mentioned studies focus on the impact of water needs on North of Africa hydrogen production.

3. Research objectives

Building upon previous studies, this study addresses these existing research gaps, offering a complementary and more integrated perspective on green hydrogen development in North of Africa, focusing on the Maghreb countries - Morocco (MAR), Tunisia (TUN) and Algeria (DZA), ranked as the most predisposed to green hydrogen production according to the analysis conducted for [31]. Using The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System (TIMES), it analyzes the techno-economic trade-offs between a local-only hydrogen consumption strategy and an export-oriented approach aligned with NHS. The analysis is structured around five distinct scenarios, differentiated by the energy sourcing for electrolysis and desalination.

The originality of this study lies in its comprehensive assessment of the competitiveness between NHS and RES-E targets. Unlike previous analyses this study investigates how hydrogen production ambitions interact with national renewable energy goals, particularly in terms of resource potential and associated costs, considering also infrastructure costs. Given that large volumes of renewable electricity are required to generate the desired levels of clean hydrogen, understanding this competition is critical for ensuring an economically viable and sustainable energy transition. Additionally, this research explores the impact of water use for hydrogen production, assessing the feasibility of fulfilling export-oriented hydrogen targets while addressing the region's water scarcity challenges. Furthermore, by enabling intra-regional electricity trade among the Maghreb countries, the analysis provides

insights into how cross-border energy flows can support both national decarbonization efforts and hydrogen production strategies.

Section 2 reviews the National Hydrogen Strategies of the Maghreb countries, their climate pledges, and the region's green hydrogen potential. Section 3 outlines the methodology, including an overview of the TIMES framework, the development of the TIMES-MAGe model, and the definition of scenarios with key assumptions and data sources. Section 4 presents and discusses the main modelling results. Finally, Section 5 concludes by summarizing key findings and suggesting directions for future research.

4. The Maghreb countries national hydrogen strategies

The Maghreb countries aim to position themselves as key players in both regional and global markets for renewable and clean hydrogen, capitalizing on their substantial renewable's potential Fig. 1, illustrates the annual production capacity estimated for gaseous hydrogen, as reported by the PtX Atlas from the Fraunhofer Institute [32].

The Maghreb countries strategic commitments is articulated in their NHS, as summarized in Table 1. Morocco was the first Maghreb country to establish a dedicated hydrogen roadmap, launching its strategy in January 2021 [33]. The country is projected to capture up to 4 % of global green hydrogen demand, with hydrogen production estimated to reach 80 PJ by 2030 and 663 PJ by 2050. Of this, 25 % is planned for domestic consumption, while the remaining 75 % is earmarked for export. Algeria followed with the release of its Green Hydrogen Strategy in September 2023 [10], aiming to establish a structured framework and a supportive environment to accelerate clean hydrogen production for both local use and export, intended to supply around 10 % of Europe's hydrogen demand as green hydrogen. Achieving this target is estimated to require a total investment of \$24.8 billion [34]. Tunisia was the last among the Maghreb nations to submit its hydrogen strategy, releasing it in May 2024 [9]. The strategy emphasizes a balanced approach between meeting domestic energy needs and expanding exports, with the aim of fostering economic and industrial growth through the integration of green hydrogen and its derivatives. Tunisia envisions becoming a net exporter of green hydrogen and a key contributor to Europe's "hydrogen backbone."

5. Methodology

The energy system model TIMES- is used to assess the cost-effective technological options and costs linked to hydrogen production and trade in Maghreb countries. Energy system modeling, coupled with scenario analysis, is a well-established approach in energy planning, enabling policymakers to evaluate the costs and benefits of various energy transition pathways. This method helps identify risks and uncertainties while providing a comprehensive understanding of the energy system to support informed decision-making [28]. This section describes the model features, its assumption as well as the scenarios modelled.

5.1. TIMES-MAGe

The TIMES-MAGe is based on the TIMES model generator, a partial equilibrium linear programming model designed to optimize the entire or specific components of a regional, national or global energy system, by minimizing total system costs over a given time horizon while satisfying technical, economic, and policy constraints [35,36]. In TIMES-MAGe, the focus is on optimizing the power sector and its interactions with centralized hydrogen production for the three Maghreb

Fig. 1. Annual potential for producing gaseous hydrogen adopted from [32].

Table 1

Strategies and roadmaps targets for green hydrogen in Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia.

	Tunisia		Morocco		Algeria	
	2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2040
Local demand (PJ)	2.4	228	25	77	N/A	36 ^a
Exports (PJ)	3.6	768	55	586	N/A	144
Renewable capacities expansion (GW)	5	100	13.4	125.5	N/A	N/A
Water use (million m ³ per year)	6.4–9.6	165–248	7	70.4	N/A	N/A
Electrolysis (GW)	3.85	87	5.2	53	N/A	2.7
References	[9]		[11]		[10]	

^a The local target of the country in on Blue hydrogen, while green hydrogen is reserved only for exportation.

countries: Morocco, Tunisia and Algeria.

The model covers the power sectors of the three Maghreb countries: Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria running from 2018 (base year) up to 2050 in two and then five time periods, i.e., 2018, 2020, 2025, 2030, ...up to 2050. To capture the variability of renewables capacity factors and electricity demand the model considers 48 times slices. Further subdivided into representative days (1 day per each of the 4 seasons) and hours (each day is modelled in 2 h segments: 0–2h, 2h–4h, 4h–6h ... 22–0h). The electricity demand projections considered in this study, excluding hydrogen-related demand, are based on a prior analysis [37, 38], which provides a detailed assessment of future electricity needs under decarbonization pathways. Electricity demand projections are defined exogenously, based on prior national planning assessments rather than endogenously derived within the model framework. While this approach ensures consistency with official targets and sectoral trajectories, it limits the model’s ability to dynamically account for demand-side responses to policy, pricing, or structural shifts.

Table 2

Techno-economic parameters of hydrogen and electricity technologies.

	CAPEX (Meuro ₂₀₁₈ /GW)		OPEX costs (Meuro ₂₀₁₈ /PJ)		Variable costs		Efficiency (%)	Lifetime	Ref
	2030	2050	2030	2050	2030	2050			
	Hydrogen Production								
SMR + CCS	965	892.5	0.71	0.62	2.5	2.5	66	30	[58,107,108]
Solar SMR	370	281	11.1	8.4	–	–	64	30	
SOEC electrolysis	1240	639.7	1.56	1.44	0	0	95	30	
Alkaline electrolysis	719.2	569.5	0.9	0.86	0	0	65	30	
PEM electrolysis	808	425.9	1.03	0.94	0	0	85	30	
Hydrogen transportation									
Blending in existing natural gas pipelines (MUSD ₂₀₁₈ /km)	0.05 ^a		–		–	–	96.5 ^a	>50	[57]
Repurposing natural gas pipelines (MUSD ₂₀₁₈ /km)	0.5		0.62		–	–	99	40	
Constructing new hydrogen pipelines (MUSD ₂₀₁₈ /km)	2.8		0.62		–	–	99	40	
Hydrogen storage									
Underground salt caverns (MUSD ₂₀₁₈ /PJ)	16.2	16.2	0.48	0.48	–	–	98	>50	[58]
Gas tank (MUSD ₂₀₂₁ /PJ)	13.4	6.8	0.4	0.4	–	–	100	25	[59]
Desalination plant (MUSD ₂₀₁₈ /Million m ³)	2.42	1.36	0.09	0.05	–	–	13	30	[60]
Electricity generation									
Natural gas	2500	2500	75		0.71		38	30	[61]
Oil	692	692	20		0.2		25	30	
Coal	700	700	20		0.4		30	25	
PV solar	751	617	15	13	–	–	100	25	
Onshore wind	950	760	38	33			100	30	
CSP	4341	3894	56	56			100	30	
Li-on batteries	765	516	18.9	15			87	8 (3000 cycles)	

5.2. General data description

Each technology is characterized by its capital, fixed and variable costs, efficiency, capacity factors, operational lifetimes, maximum capacity potential and emission intensity Table 2. And the inputs and outputs of the considered technologies are illustrated in Fig. A2. The power sector technologies considered in this study include fossil-based sources (coal, oil, natural gas), renewable sources (solar PV, concentrated solar power, onshore wind, hydropower), and hydrogen production technologies (electrolysis and SMR coupled with CCS). The techno-economic parameters of the existing and projected fossil fuel-based and renewable have been collected from Refs. [25,39], and data related for hydrogen production are found in Ref. [40]. The current installed power plants and the retirement capacities in The Maghreb were sourced from the Global Power Plant Database [41], Harvard Dataverse [42], and IRENA reports [43–48] [43–45,47–49]. The environmental parameters related to emissions were taken from the EDGAR [50]. Data according to techno-economic parameters for distribution and transmissions technologies was provided by the JRC-EU-TIMES model [51]. A 5 % social discount rate was adopted in line with international modeling practices (e.g., IEA [52]) and regional studies, reflecting a public policy perspective appropriate for assessing long-term, infrastructure-intensive energy transitions in North Africa, where public and concessional financing often play a central role [53,54]. The model is calibrated in euro (€) with 2018 as its base year, selected for its complete, harmonized datasets across Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria. Key capacity inputs were updated to 2023 values and validated against observed 2023 electricity demand, achieving deviations of no more than 3 %. All cost data remain expressed in 2018 EUR; to convert to 2023 EUR, an inflation factor of 1.22 should be applied [55]. Electrolyzers are assumed to operate with a 90 % annual utilization factor (equivalent to 7884 full-load hours) since lower hydrogen production costs can be obtained with high full load hours [56].

The water demand is supplied by seawater reverse osmosis (SWRO) desalination. The investment cost of a hydrogen pipeline is based on the European Hydrogen Backbone study, factoring the pipeline and compressor, as well as CAPEX and OPEX [57]. The necessary length of the hydrogen infrastructure is estimated based on the distance between

the central nodes in each country. The cost estimation is based on the approximate length of the hydrogen network and the utilization and flows on the joint hydrogen-gas infrastructure Fig. 3.

5.3. Clean hydrogen production

Hydrogen production technologies vary in terms of their development stage, required feedstocks and resources (such as natural gas, oil, coal, and water), as well as their associated greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions Fig. A1. The most commonly used classifications, “grey,” “blue,” and “green” hydrogen, refer to different production methods based on their carbon footprint. Currently, fossil fuels remain the most cost-effective option for hydrogen production, with costs ranging between 1 and 3 EURO per kilogram of H₂.

As a result, fossil fuels still account for 95 % of global hydrogen supply [62,63], contributing to approximately 900 million tons of CO₂ emissions annually [64]. The topic of hydrogen production has gained increasing attention in research [65–68], with various studies analyzing different production methods. Some focus on specific technologies, while others examine broader trends. Notably, blue hydrogen has been explored as a transitional solution before achieving a complete shift to green hydrogen [69–71].

Blue hydrogen is produced through steam methane reforming (SMR) combined with carbon capture and storage (CCS), using natural gas as its primary feedstock. However, despite CCS implementation, methane combustion in the process still results in significant CO₂ emissions, ranging between 8.3 and 10.1 kgCO₂ per kg of hydrogen produced [72, 73]. One of the major challenges of CCS technology is its high cost. At the early stages of a project, investment requirements are particularly steep, making large-scale deployment financially demanding. The integration of CCS has been shown to increase capital expenditure (CAPEX) by approximately 69 % compared to hydrogen production without carbon capture, further complicating its economic viability [58,74].

In this study, we assess an alternative to SMR with CCS by incorporating solar energy for heat duty coupled with CCS, reducing CO₂ emissions by 34–53 % and methane consumption by at least 34 % [72]. While this approach lowers emissions, it still relies on methane, making it more accurately classified as blue hydrogen rather than green. Green

Fig. 2. Overview of hydrogen production technologies considered in this study adopted from [81].

Fig. 3. Existing and planned natural gas pipeline infrastructure between the Maghreb and Europe [23].

hydrogen can be produced from biomass gasification and through water electrolysis powered by RES-E and has recently gained significant attention in the literature [65,75,76]. Our analysis considers three main electrolysis technologies: Alkaline water electrolysis (ALK), the most established with approximately 70 % market share [77], polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) electrolysis, and solid oxide electrolyzes cell (SOEC). This study focuses on technologies suitable for large-scale hydrogen production in the near to medium term Fig. 2. While grey hydrogen remains the most cost-effective production method today [78, 79], it was excluded from our analysis due to its misalignment with The Maghreb countries’ transition toward a sustainable energy system [80] and exports to EU. Additionally, alternative methods, such as blue and green hydrogen, are expected to become more cost-competitive in the future [78].

5.4. Green hydrogen storage

The Maghreb region holds Africa’s largest salt cavern potential, particularly in Morocco, offering a highly cost-effective and scalable solution for large-scale green hydrogen storage. Salt caverns are widely recognized as one of the most efficient options for storing gaseous hydrogen due to their low investment costs, high sealing potential, and minimal cushion gas requirements [82]. Given this vast potential Table 3, this study incorporates hydrogen storage in salt caverns as a long-term solution to balance supply and demand fluctuations. The modeling results reveal significant differences in hydrogen and electricity storage requirements under two strategic approaches: local-only consumption and export-oriented strategies.

Table 3 Overview of salt formations potentially suitable for the creation of salt caverns [61].

Country	Number of salt formations potentially suitable for the creation of salt caverns	Overall theoretical storage potential	Preliminary estimation of the technical storage capacity
Morocco	6	Good	>3600 PJ
Algeria	7	Good	>360 PJ
Tunisia	2	Limited to medium	4 to 40 PJ

5.5. Hydrogen transportation

Recent studies have concluded that existing natural gas pipelines and distribution networks can accommodate hydrogen transport with few modifications [83]. This concept has been explored in previous research, with initiatives such as MedHySol [84] (Mediterranean Hydrogen Solar), the Europe Hydrogen Manifesto, and studies on Clean Hydrogen Deployment in the Europe-MENA Region (2030–2050), proposing hydrogen injection into Algeria’s natural gas pipelines as a cost-effective solution for the Maghreb, eliminating the need for extensive infrastructure upgrades. Currently, four operational pipelines connect North Africa to Europe Fig. 3. In Africa, the onshore segments range from 550 km in the Medgaz pipeline (0.8 m diameter) to 1037 km in the Transmed pipeline (1.2 m diameter), with an average onshore distance of 770 km. Offshore transport distances vary, from 45 km in the MEG pipeline (0.5 m diameter) to 210 km in Medgaz.

This study considers three hydrogen transportation methods for intra-regional trade among Maghreb countries and potential exports to Europe. Hydrogen can be transported through existing natural gas pipelines by blending it until a maximum of 40 % in volume and 3.5 % in energy content [40], repurposing natural gas infrastructure, or constructing new dedicated pipelines. Fig. 4 outlines the decision-making process for hydrogen infrastructure investments, presenting three possible outcomes. While the blending approach requires no additional pipeline construction, investments in compressor stations are necessary, depending on the transport distance. Alternatively, when hydrogen volumes surpass the blending limit or when blending capacity is unavailable, repurposing existing natural gas pipelines becomes a viable solution. This approach can be up to four times more cost-effective than building entirely new hydrogen pipelines.

In the case of repurposing or constructing new dedicated hydrogen pipelines parallel to the existing natural gas pipelines, the energy content ratio between natural gas and hydrogen is thus calculated based on Equation (1). This approach considers the significant difference in energy content between natural gas and hydrogen. Natural gas energy content is approximately 35.8 MJ/cubic meter, whereas hydrogen has a lower energy content of approximately 10.8 MJ/cubic meter.

$$Energy\ Content\ Ratio = \frac{Energy\ content\ of\ natural\ gas}{Energy\ content\ of\ hydrogen} \approx 3.31 \tag{1}$$

Using this ratio, the estimated hydrogen capacity based on the

Fig. 4. Hydrogen investment decision tree adopted from [57].

Table 4

Assumed technical characteristics and hydrogen transport capacities of Maghreb–Europe gas pipelines [85].

	Existing natural gas pipelines (PJ/year)	Distance (km)		Maximum hydrogen capacities (PJ/year)	
		Offshore	Onshore	Blending	Repurposing/ New dedicated
Transmed	1147	154	536	40.6	346
MEG	456	31	505	16	137
Galsi	304	245	–	10.6	92
MedGaz	304	210	–	10.6	92

natural gas capacity is calculated using Equation (2).

$$Hydrogen\ capacity\ (PJ/year) = \frac{Natural\ gas\ pipeline\ capacity\ (PJ/year)}{Energy\ content\ ratio} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, to provide clarity and consistency, the key parameters and final assumptions for the hydrogen pipelines are summarized in Table 4.

5.6. Scenarios description

This study models five distinct scenarios Table 5 to assess the impact of energy sources and water supply configurations on green hydrogen production, installed capacities, and costs across The Maghreb countries. The scenarios vary by the type of electricity (RES-E vs. grid electricity) powering electrolysis and desalination, as well as the water source (surface water vs. desalinated water). Each scenario is run under a local-only consumption strategy, while scenarios meeting EU regulations for green hydrogen production are also evaluated under a local and export-oriented strategy.

5.6.1. Baseline scenario – grid-based electrolysis & surface water – local demand only (S1)

- Assumption: Hydrogen production relies on grid electricity, making it non-compliant with EU certification. Electrolysis uses surface water, excluding desalination. Production is limited to domestic consumption, with no exports.

- Objective: This scenario highlights the limitations of grid-powered electrolysis and surface water reliance, failing to meet EU standards and national hydrogen targets while worsening water stress. Though not a viable option, it serves as a baseline to assess the impact of desalination and renewable-powered electrolysis on costs and system performance.

5.6.2. Baseline scenario- RES-powered electrolysis & surface water – local + export demand (S2)

- Assumption: Hydrogen production is fully powered by RES-E, meeting EU green hydrogen standards. It includes both local consumption and exports, aligning with the NHS of Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria. Surface water is the sole water source, excluding desalination.

- Objective: This scenario serves as a baseline for export-oriented hydrogen strategies, highlighting the trade-offs between local-only and export-driven production. It enables comparison of the additional infrastructure, energy capacity, and costs required for hydrogen exports, while also providing a benchmark to assess the

Table 5

Overview of modelled scenarios and key assumptions.

Attribute	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
Electrolysis power source (grid)	Y	N	N	N	Y
Electrolysis power source (RES-E)	N	Y	Y	Y	Y
Water source (surface water)	Y	Y	N	N	Y
Water source (desalinated water)	N	N	Y	Y	Y
Desalination power source (grid)	N	N	Y	N	Y
Desalination power source (RES-E)	N	N	N	Y	Y
Tunisia	Local only	Local & Export	Local & Export	Local & Export	Local only
Morocco	Local only	Local & Export	Local & Export	Local & Export	Local only
Algeria	Local only	Local & Export	Local & Export	Local & Export	Local only

impact of desalination on system costs and renewable energy demand.

5.6.3. Policy-driven scenario- RES-E powered electrolysis & grid-powered desalination – local + export demand (S3)

- **Assumption:** Electrolysis is fully powered by RES-E, meeting EU green hydrogen standards. Unlike the previous scenario, desalination is introduced, but powered by the national grid. Hydrogen production covers both local demand and export targets.
- **Objective:** This scenario balances sustainability and feasibility by integrating grid-powered desalination to address water scarcity while ensuring compliance with EU regulations. It assesses the cost and energy impact of desalination on hydrogen production, including system costs, infrastructure investments, and renewable capacity needs. Unlike previous baselines, it offers a practical framework aligned with national hydrogen strategies and EU import goals.

5.6.4. Full RES integration scenario- RES-powered electrolysis & RES-powered desalination – local + export demand (S4)

- **Assumption:** Electrolysis and desalination are fully powered by RES-E, eliminating fossil fuel reliance.
- **Objective:** This scenario tests the feasibility of a fully decarbonized hydrogen production system in the Maghreb. It evaluates trade-offs in costs, required RE capacity, and impacts on hydrogen production costs while ensuring compliance with green hydrogen standards. The analysis determines whether a fully renewable approach is viable or if interim solutions, like grid-powered desalination, are necessary.

5.6.5. Flexible energy sourcing scenario cost-optimal energy mix - local demand only (S5)

- **Assumption:** This scenario removes predefined energy constraints, allowing the model to determine the most cost-effective mix for meeting local hydrogen demand. Unlike previous scenarios, it optimizes energy inputs for electrolysis and desalination without imposing specific sourcing requirements. Export production is excluded due to regulatory uncertainties.
- **Objective:** This scenario identifies the least-cost energy mix for hydrogen production in The Maghreb, assessing trade-offs between grid and renewable-powered electrolysis and desalination. By letting the model freely allocate energy, it reveals whether cost-driven optimization aligns with National Hydrogen Strategies or leans on

fossil-based grid electricity, potentially conflicting with long-term decarbonization goals.

Across all scenarios, this study explores the competitiveness of National Hydrogen Strategies targets in relation to the (NDCs) and (LT-LEDS) of The Maghreb evaluating their alignment with national renewable energy commitments, investment requirements, and hydrogen export strategies. A key focus is placed on the impact of large-scale hydrogen production on unitary electricity costs, considering both domestic consumption and export-oriented pathways. To ensure consistency in scenario comparisons, the following assumptions are made.

- **Inclusion of NDCs and LT-LEDS targets:** Across all scenarios, the renewable electricity targets defined under NDCs and LT-LEDS (as outlined in Table 6) are strictly enforced, ensuring that hydrogen production is assessed within the broader national decarbonization context.
- **Energy Storage Considerations:** All scenarios assume the integration of energy storage systems, including battery storage for electricity and underground or gas tank storage for hydrogen.
- **Intra-Regional Electricity Trading:** Electricity trading between Maghreb countries is enabled, allowing for cross-border optimization of energy supply and demand. However, the model does not allow for the expansion of interconnection capacities, meaning that electricity trade is limited to existing and planned interconnectors.

6. Results and discussion

6.1. Hydrogen production costs

Hydrogen production costs in the Maghreb exhibit significant variations depending on the scenario, reflecting the interplay between energy sourcing, water supply, and demand ambitions Table 7 for 2050, and Table A2 for 2030.

Under local-only strategies, green hydrogen production in Morocco and Tunisia ranges between 1.8 and 2.5 €/kg H₂ by 2050, while blue hydrogen in Algeria, meeting its national demand, has the lower cost, estimated at 1.7–2.1 €/kg H₂. However, in export-oriented scenarios, where hydrogen production scales up to meet both domestic and international demand costs rise significantly, reaching 3.7–9.3 €/kg H₂, with higher cost associated with Tunisia. In export-oriented scenarios, where hydrogen production scales up to meet both domestic and international demand, system-wide costs rise sharply. This increase stems from structural pressures revealed by the model’s endogenous optimization. First, supplying hydrogen at large volumes for export requires the expansion of dedicated renewable energy capacity, leading to higher capital investment and lower system efficiency due to curtailment or underutilization. Second, electrolyzers must be oversized to meet export peaks, reducing their annual capacity factor and raising the cost per kilogram of hydrogen produced. Third, high hydrogen output increases the average cost of electricity delivered to electrolysis, as cheaper

Table 6
National targets for renewable electricity (RES-E) and hydrogen production (local consumption & Export) in Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria [86–90].

		Hydrogen projection			NDCs and LT-LEDS targets
		Local	Export	Total	
Tunisia	2030	2.4	3.6	6	35 % RES-E
	2050	228	768	996	80 % RES-E
Morocco	2030	25	55	80	52 % RE capacities
	2050	77	586	663	80 % RE capacities
Algeria	2030	–	–	–	27 % RES-E
	2050 ^a	36 ^b	144	–	27 % RES-E ^c

^a Algeria’s National Hydrogen Strategy (NHS) sets a target for 2040; however, for consistency and model calibration purposes, all NHS targets in this study are assumed to be achieved by 2050.

^b Algeria’s local hydrogen demand is for blue hydrogen.

^c The country has not set a renewable electricity (RES-E) target for 2050. In this study, we assume that the 2030 RES-E target remains unchanged through 2050.

Table 7
Unitary Hydrogen Production Costs Across All Scenarios for Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria in 2050 under Local-Only and Export-Oriented Strategies. Costs are color-coded from green (lowest) to red (highest), applied horizontally to highlight relative cost competitiveness.

		€/2018/ kg of H ₂				
		S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
Tunisia	Local Only	2.52	2.01	2.23	2.28	2.20
	Local and Export	N/A	8.43	7.9	9.4	N/A
Morocco	Local Only	2.12	1.83	2.03	2.16	2.01
	Local and Export	N/A	6.92	6.93	7.4	N/A
Algeria	Local Only	1.83	1.74	2.13	2.13	1.82
	Local and Export	N/A	3.72	4.18	4.18	N/A

renewable resources are exhausted and more expensive alternatives are tapped. These effects compound in export scenarios, explaining the observed cost increases in high-export pathways, as in an international energy (IEA) study [6], indicating that renewable electricity-based green H2 will cost more, often in the range of 4–10 €/kg H₂.

These results align with various studies reporting Morocco’s hydrogen production costs between 2.54 and 13.8 €/kg [91–93], with some estimates for local-only strategies ranging from 2.9 to 5.9 €/kg [94, 95]. Lower estimates of 2.2–3.1 €/kg for 2050 [96,97] are consistent with this study’s findings. For Algeria, blue hydrogen production costs (1.2–2.8 €/kg) align with [98], while green hydrogen estimates (1.5–15.3 €/kg_{H2}) [96,99] validate this study’s range. Limited literature exists for Tunisia but reported costs of 1.8–5.2 €/kg [100,101] match the local-only scenario. However, for export strategies, production costs exceed literature values due to the intensity of hydrogen targets and the extensive RES-E expansion required for electrolysis.

The lowest-cost scenario involves renewable-powered electrolysis using surface water, where green hydrogen production costs reach 2.0 €/kg in Tunisia and 1.8 €/kg in Morocco, under local strategies. However, in export-oriented strategies, where hydrogen targets are significantly higher, with production costs escalating up to more than 6.9 €/kg, in the two countries. Algeria’s lower costs stem not from a structural cost advantage or higher techno-economic competitiveness, but from its relatively modest hydrogen production targets compared to Morocco and Tunisia. Scenario 4, which assumes both electrolysis and desalination are entirely powered by RES-E, represents the most capital-intensive pathway, with local hydrogen production below to 2.2 €/kg in the three countries. Under export-oriented strategies, costs increase further to 9.4 €/kg in Tunisia, 7.4 €/kg in Morocco, and 4.18 €/kg in Algeria, reflecting a 13 % increase compared to Scenario 3, where desalination is powered by grid electricity. These findings underscore the economic challenges of achieving full compliance with EU green hydrogen certification, demonstrating that while a fully renewable hydrogen supply chain ensures sustainability, it may impose substantial financial burdens on North African economies.

Scenario 5 optimizes hydrogen production by allowing the model to determine the most cost-effective mix of RES-E and grid electricity for electrolysis and desalination, applied exclusively to the local-only strategy. This flexibility results in hydrogen production cost reductions of 2 %, 7 %, and 14 % in Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria, respectively, compared to Scenario 4, and 2 %, 1 %, and 14 % when compared to Scenario 3. These findings underscore the economic benefits of integrating grid electricity strategically, offering cost savings while maintaining a balance between financial feasibility and sustainability objectives.

6.2. Electricity affordability and energy transition

The integration of large-scale hydrogen production into the power sector necessitates additional generation capacity, reshaping electricity pricing dynamics and introducing new interdependencies between

electrolysis deployment and power system development. Electrolysis directly influences electricity production costs, while in turn, electricity prices dictate the economic viability of hydrogen production [102]. Balancing these interactions is essential for ensuring both affordability and the broader energy transition.

The highest electricity costs emerge under Scenario 4 Table 8 for 2050 and Table A1 for 2030, where electrolysis and desalination are fully powered by RES-E while ensuring compliance with national RES-E targets. This configuration intensifies competition for renewable resources, driving electricity production costs up by 40 % in Morocco and Tunisia and 13 % in Algeria compared to grid-powered electrolysis. In contrast, the lowest electricity costs are observed in Scenario 2, where electrolysis is powered exclusively by RES-E without desalination, aligning with the lowest hydrogen production costs.

Hydrogen export ambitions further exacerbate electricity cost pressures. Under the export-oriented strategy, unitary electricity costs increase by 70 % in Algeria, 162 % in Tunisia, and 220 % in Morocco compared to the local-only strategy, emphasizing the economic challenges associated with large-scale hydrogen exports. However, Scenario 5, which introduces flexibility in electrolysis energy sourcing, mitigates these cost increases, reducing electricity costs by 7 % in Tunisia, 4 % in Morocco, and 5 % in Algeria compared to Scenario 4, demonstrating the cost-saving potential of a hybrid energy approach.

Despite these findings, a critical policy gap remains regarding the integration of hydrogen production into national electricity systems. Without strategic regulatory frameworks to optimize resource allocation and mitigate cost escalations, large-scale hydrogen deployment may strain power systems and slow down the broader energy transition. Aligning hydrogen expansion with national energy priorities while maintaining affordability will be essential for ensuring a sustainable and economically viable clean energy future in the Maghreb [102].

6.3. Investment and energy system implications

The comparative analysis of green hydrogen investments in Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria highlights the financial and strategic challenges these countries face in aligning their hydrogen ambitions with their (RES-E) targets. Tunisia requires €55 billion of cumulative investment (from 2025 to 2050) for a local-only strategy and €270 billion for an export-oriented approach by 2050, representing 20 % and 68 % of its projected GDP, respectively Fig. 5. Morocco’s investment needs are €54 billion for local production and €118 billion for export, accounting for 7 % and 16 % of GDP, while Algeria requires €40 billion and €62 billion, representing 4.4 % and 7 % of GDP. These figures underscore the disproportionate economic burden on Tunisia due to its ambitious hydrogen strategy, whereas Morocco follows a more balanced approach, and Algeria adopts a more cautious stance, perspective. Achieving these targets requires substantial investments in electrolysis, desalination, hydrogen storage, and large-scale renewable energy deployment. Under the export-oriented strategy, Tunisia must develop 1600 PJ of RES-E by 2050, 670 times of 2024 production, while Morocco requires 800 PJ (27 times of 2024 value), reflecting the scale of hydrogen production and electricity demand. Renewable power accounts for the majority of investment costs, 85 % in both countries, followed by electrolysis (16 %), desalination (0.13 %), and storage. Storage costs, while relatively minor, amount to €52 million for Tunisia and €18 million for Morocco under export-oriented strategies, covering both electricity and hydrogen storage. This goes in line with the components of hydrogen costs [103], electricity is always the biggest component, influencing largely the hydrogen production costs, thus the investments required.

Comparing these figures with NHS reveals key disparities Table A3. Tunisia’s NHS estimates €2024157 billion (€2018126 billion) for hydrogen investments in renewables, electrolysis, and desalination (excluding storage), while model projections suggest 1.3 times higher costs, mainly due to differences in renewable energy cost assumptions. Morocco’s NHS projections for electrolysis and desalination (€202118 billion)

Table 8
Unitary Electricity Costs Across All Scenarios for Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria in 2050 under Local-Only and Export-Oriented Strategies. Costs are color-coded from green (lowest) to red (highest), applied horizontally to highlight relative cost competitiveness.

€ ₂₀₁₈ /kWh		S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
Tunisia	Local	0.12	0.11	0.14	0.17	0.13
	Local and Export	N/A	0.28	0.30	0.34	N/A
Morocco	Local	0.10	0.10	0.12	0.15	0.11
	Local and Export	N/A	0.31	0.33	0.47	N/A
Algeria	Local	0.18	0.17	0.19	0.20	0.18
	Local and Export	N/A	0.24	0.26	0.34	N/A

Fig. 5. Cumulative investment requirements by (2025-2050): Comparing local-only and export-oriented hydrogen strategies in the Maghreb, (left axis: Investments in hydrogen and electricity production | right axis: Investments in desalination and storage).

(€₂₀₁₈17 billion) align precisely with model estimates, but discrepancies arise in RES-E expansion, where the model suggests €52 billion, compared to the NHS estimate of €₂₀₂₁ 68 billion (€₂₀₁₈ 64 billion), likely due to variations in discount rates. Export strategies significantly amplify financial requirements, with Tunisia incurring additional costs of €200 billion for RES capacities, €40 billion for electrolysis, and €0.3 billion for desalination, whereas Morocco's corresponding investments are €50 billion, €15 billion, and €0.2 billion. However, this approach risks non-compliance with EU regulations, which mandate RES-E-powered electrolysis for hydrogen imports. Flexibility in energy sourcing can optimize costs, as demonstrated by Scenario S5, where overall investments decrease by 6 % in Tunisia and 2 % in Morocco, emphasizing the importance of adaptive strategies.

Algeria's investment requirements remain comparatively lower, reflecting its cautious approach to hydrogen development. While the National Hydrogen Strategy outlines moderate funding for green hydrogen, model results suggest slightly lower needs, excluding additional investments required for blue hydrogen production. Additionally, Algeria lacks a detailed RES-E investment plan, though modeling suggests €6 billion of capital needs to meet its RES-E targets. Export-oriented strategies introduce further costs, adding €18 billion for RES capacities and €100 million for desalination, reinforcing Algeria's conservative approach compared to its neighbors.

Overall, Tunisia's aggressive leadership in hydrogen development demands significant international financial support and policy integration, whereas Morocco's pragmatic model balances ambition with economic sustainability. Algeria's cautious approach, while minimizing financial strain, may limit its competitive position in the regional hydrogen market. Outcomes show that notably, hydrogen storage requirements decline sharply when transitioning from a domestic-focused strategy to one prioritizing exports, a clear indication of how the TIMES model optimizes production, assuming a seamless synchronization between generation, storage, and export logistics. However, this assumption overlooks real-world operational constraints, such as fluctuating export demand, transportation delays, and production irregularity due to extreme or uncertain situations, all of which could necessitate greater storage capacity. In Tunisia, the local-only strategy requires 4.5 PJ of stored hydrogen by 2050, utilizing 12.5 % of the country's technical salt

cavern capacity. However, under the export-oriented strategy, storage demand drops nearly fivefold to 0.8 PJ, as hydrogen is produced and exported directly with minimal buffering. A similar pattern is observed in Morocco, where hydrogen storage requirements range between 7 and 9 PJ under local-only conditions, just 0.25 % of its technical potential, before dropping to 2 PJ under the export scenario. In Algeria, hydrogen storage remains consistently low, with a mere 1 PJ stored under the export strategy, just 0.03 % of its potential.

A critical insight emerges from the absence of battery storage for electricity under all scenarios, which consider the possibility of intra-regional electricity trade up to existing and planned interconnectors capacity. The model finds that instead of storing excess electricity in batteries, the most cost-effective approach is direct electricity exports, generating revenue for the net exporter countries. However, additional scenarios, disabling the possibility of intra-regional electricity trading, reveal that battery deployment as an alternative. For example, under the local plus export strategy, battery installations in Tunisia and Morocco range from 300 MW to 500 MW (particularly in scenarios where electrolysis and desalination rely on RES-E), while Algeria did not install batteries due to the limited production of RES-E in line with the NDCs target and the moderate target of hydrogen. This result suggests that, for the Maghreb, utilizing surplus electricity for hydrogen production via electrolysis is a more economically viable strategy than investing in battery storage, aligning with national hydrogen strategies and ensuring maximum resource utilization [104].

Establishing a green hydrogen market in the Maghreb entails significant upfront investments. However, the potential long-term benefits for the region are substantial. Our results demonstrate consistent net gains across all modelled scenarios, reaching approximately €90 billion by 2050 upon full achievement of national hydrogen production and export targets Fig. 6.

These findings align with existing literature, such as Bob van der Zwaan et al. [21], who estimate that a strategic hydrogen partnership between the European Union and North African countries could yield annual revenues of up to €50 billion for the region. Beyond economic returns, the development of a green hydrogen economy holds strong social value, potentially creating approximately 400,000 jobs in the hydrogen and renewable energy sectors throughout The Maghreb [77].

Fig. 6. Modelled revenues from hydrogen Export under different scenarios (2030 & 2050).

These outcomes underscore the dual promise of green hydrogen as both a financial opportunity and a catalyst for sustainable socio-economic development in a region strategically positioned to become a global hydrogen hub.

6.4. Water-energy nexus

The following section presents a comprehensive analysis of the impact of water sources and hydrogen production targets on electricity consumption and costs, hydrogen production costs, and overall water use across the three countries. The shift from surface water to

desalination leads to an increase in electricity consumption. Our findings just indicate an additional energy demand of 0.05 % and 2 % with 0.26 PJ and 2.5 PJ required to power the desalination process to fulfill the local target only and the export-oriented strategies, respectively in The Maghreb. In Morocco and Tunisia, this increase varies between 0.5 and 2 PJ under the local target only and from 35 to 52 PJ for the export-oriented strategy while in Algeria, the rise is approximately low. Thus, the share of electricity allocated to desalination remains consistently 0.2 % of the total electricity required for hydrogen production, irrespective of the strategy (local-only or export-oriented) or the scenario. This uniform share suggests that while absolute electricity consumption for

Table 9

Comparative Analysis of Water Use, Electricity Generation, RES-E Deployment, and Hydrogen Production Costs Across Scenarios and Strategies in the Maghreb (2050). The values are color-coded vertically from green (Best/lowest) to red (Worst/highest), allowing comparison across scenarios, countries, and strategies.

Countries	Strategies	Scenarios	Surface Water use (Million tons)	Electricity generation (PJ)	RES-E generation (PJ)	Hydrogen production cost (€ ₂₀₁₈ /kg)	Electricity production cost (€ ₂₀₁₈ /kWh)
Tunisia	Local Only	S ₁	17	640	512.5	2.52	0.12
		S ₂	17	603	483	2.01	0.11
		S ₃	34	640.5	483.6	2.28	0.14
		S ₄	34	605	524.6	2.23	0.17
		S ₅	34	604	483	2.2	0.13
	Local and Export	S ₂	73	1770.8	1416.8	8.43	0.28
		S ₃	145	1707.2	1365.6	9.3	0.3
		S ₄	145	2048	1638.5	8.44	0.34
Morocco	Local Only	S ₁	9	561	447.6	2.12	0.1
		S ₂	9	552	440.2	1.83	0.1
		S ₃	18	554	440.7	2.03	0.12
		S ₄	18	576.7	464.9	2.16	0.15
		S ₅	18	552	439	2.01	0.11
	Local and export	S ₂	38	966.8	761.6	6.92	0.31
		S ₃	78	1011	805.7	7.4	0.33
		S ₄	78	1035	830	6.93	0.47
Algeria	Local Only	S ₁	4.7	682	188.3	1.83	0.18
		S ₂	4.7	676	182.5	1.74	0.17
		S ₃	9.4	676.3	182.6	2.13	0.19
		S ₄	9.4	677	184.5	2.13	0.2
		S ₅	9.4	676	183	1.82	0.18
	Local and export	S ₂	14	962	259.7	3.72	0.24
		S ₃	27.5	966.6	263.8	4.17	0.26
		S ₄	27.5	968.5	265.8	4.18	0.34

Fig. 7. Water consumption for hydrogen production in Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria across scenarios and strategies (2050).

hydrogen production scales up significantly in export-driven cases, the proportional impact on total electricity demand remains marginal.

This difference between the increase observed in Morocco and Tunisia compared to Algeria can be explained by the difference in target, where Algeria is focused on blue hydrogen for local demand and the export target is from 3 to 5 times lower than the targets for the other countries. This additional electricity demand for desalination translates into an increase in unitary electricity costs of approximately 7–14 % when compared to scenarios reliant exclusively on surface water for the local strategy for The Maghreb countries, and more pronounced impact is observed in local plus export-oriented strategy, which proves the heaviest economic impact of exportation in electricity production costs Table 9.

When desalination is powered by dedicated RES-E, the lower capacity factors of RES-E technologies compared to conventional grid electricity mix led to additional generation capacity, ultimately increasing RES-E electricity production. In grid-powered scenarios (S1 and S3), total electricity generation is higher than in RES-E-powered scenarios due to the model's cost-optimal expansion strategy. S1 treats electrolysis as an additional grid demand, requiring greater RES-E capacity to meet both hydrogen production and general electricity needs. In contrast, S2 limits RES-E deployment strictly to electrolysis, minimizing overcapacity but reducing overall RES expansion. The lower capacity factor increases electricity generation needs, raising production costs Table 9. Export-oriented strategies see sharper cost escalations, with production costs nearly doubling in Tunisia and Algeria and tripling in Morocco compared to the local-only strategy.

These results underscore the importance of assessing the trade-offs between water security and energy consumption, especially in the context of the Maghreb region, where electricity tariffs, infrastructure limitations, and water scarcity challenges significantly influence the feasibility of large-scale hydrogen production. The introduction of desalination also significantly affects unitary hydrogen production costs, with the results indicating an increase of approximately 14 %, 16 % and 11 % in Tunisia, Morocco and Algeria respectively in desalination-based scenarios compared to their surface-water counterparts. For export-oriented strategy the hydrogen production is the highest in Tunisia with 8.43 €/kWh and the lowest in Algeria with 4.18 €/kWh.

Water usage patterns exhibit significant variations across the analyzed scenarios. In the local-plus-export scenarios, total water demand increases substantially, with requirements reaching 308 million tons, 170 million tons, and 60 million tons for Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria, respectively. Although these figures represent only 5 %, 1.9 %,

and 0.2 % of the total available surface water[†] resources in these countries, they correspond an increase of nearly 300 % for Morocco and Tunisia and 200 % for Algeria compared to the local-oriented strategy. This seemingly low share does not account for existing water stress, seasonal variability, competition with other vital sectors such as agriculture and drinking water, and the long-term sustainability of water withdrawals under climate change projections.

The Maghreb region remains fundamentally water-scarce when evaluated through per capita water availability. According to the Falkenmark Index [105], Tunisia (400 m³/hab.yr) and Algeria (404 m³/hab.yr) are facing severe water scarcity, as their annual water availability per person falls below the 500 m³ threshold, while Morocco (811 m³ per capita) remains below the 1000 m³ benchmark for water scarcity. Water resources are already subject to intense competition from sectors such as agriculture, industry, and domestic consumption, and additional consumption for hydrogen could exacerbate this burden (Fig. 7). these indicators highlight the fragile balance between available water resources and projected hydrogen production needs, underscoring the need for integrated water-energy strategies, such as desalination or waste water treatment, to avoid unsustainable resource competition.

6.5. Energy targets and allocation

Achieving the dual objectives of RES-E and green hydrogen production targets in the Maghreb region requires an analysis of installed capacities and production distribution. These targets compete for the region's renewable energy potential, necessitating strategic planning to optimize electricity allocation. The results presented in Fig. 8 demonstrate that the available technical potential of renewable energy resources in the Maghreb is sufficient to simultaneously achieve the defined RES-E and hydrogen production targets under both the local-only and local-plus-export strategies. However, a clear pattern emerges when comparing the RES capacities requirements across these two strategies, with the export-oriented feature driving a substantial increase in total installed capacities over the modelling horizon. By 2050, the total RES installed capacity reaches approximately 250 GW across the Maghreb countries, doubling the 110 GW capacity observed under the local-only strategy, with the additional capacity consisting of

[†] The total available surface water resources serve as an initial reference for potential hydrogen production. Tunisia's surface water resources are estimated at 2700 million tons [109], Algeria's at 11,000 million tons [110], and Morocco's at 4000 million tons [111].

Fig. 8. Capacities distribution for electricity and clean hydrogen production for 2050 for Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria, left axis represent the electricity capacities and right axis capacities for hydrogen production.

70 GW of onshore wind, 40 GW of solar PV, and 30 GW of CSP. Both Tunisia and Morocco achieve the maximum solar PV and onshore wind endogenous potential, leading to the deployment of CSP.

In parallel, hydrogen production capacities increase, on average, sixfold when transitioning from the local-only to the local-plus-export strategy. Among the three countries, Tunisia exhibits the most pronounced increase, driven by its more ambitious hydrogen export targets

compared to Morocco and Algeria. These expansions underscore the critical role of export-driven hydrogen production in shaping the renewable energy landscape of the region. It is essential to note that this comparison between the local-only and local-plus-export strategies is based on Scenario 4, which represents the most RES-intensive scenario, where both electrolysis and desalination processes are powered entirely by RES-E and ensuring the achievement of RES-E targets. The magnitude

Fig. 9. Electricity and clean hydrogen production distribution for Tunisia, Morocco and Algeria for 2050 across modelled scenarios.

of renewable energy capacity expansion varies across the different scenarios. For instance, the transition toward aligning with EU legislation for green hydrogen production, which mandates that electrolysis processes be powered exclusively by renewable electricity (from S1 to S2),

necessitates a significant expansion of RE capacities across The Maghreb countries (42 % in Tunisia, 22 % in Morocco, and 14 % in Algeria compared to S2). As expected, this renewable energy expansion is accompanied by a corresponding reduction in natural gas-based

Table 10

Intra-regional electricity trade matrix for The Maghreb countries for 2050 (PJ) – Local only strategy.

Exporter ↓/Importer →	Tunisia	Morocco	Algeria
Tunisia	–	0	31
Morocco	0	–	51
Algeria	0	0	–

Table 11

Intra-regional electricity trade matrix for The Maghreb countries for 2050 (PJ) – Local + Export strategy.

Exporter ↓/Importer →	Tunisia	Morocco	Algeria
Tunisia	–	0	31
Morocco	0	–	0
Algeria	0	54	–

capacities across the three countries. Specifically, Tunisia exhibits a 47 % decrease, followed by Algeria with an 8 % reduction, and Morocco with a more modest 3 % decline. The disparity in the magnitude of these reductions can be attributed to differences in each country's power sector configuration and the scale of hydrogen production targets adopted. Tunisia's pronounced decline in natural gas capacity is primarily driven by its ambitious green hydrogen export targets. Morocco's limited decrease reflects its comparatively lower reliance on natural gas natural gas for domestic blue hydrogen production (more cost-effective), even as electrolysis for electricity generation, and Algeria's moderate reduction is explained by its continued use of capacity is simultaneously scaled up to support green hydrogen exports. The results indicate substantial differences in electrolysis capacity between the local-only and export-oriented strategies, with increases of 500 % in both Tunisia and Morocco and 400 % in Algeria under the export scenario. Under the local-only strategy, Algeria meets its hydrogen targets exclusively through blue hydrogen, with SMR coupled with (CCS) identified as the cost-optimal pathway, aligning with the country's focus on satisfying domestic demand.

PEM electrolysis represents the cost-effective technology in all scenario runs, which may be justified by its high operational flexibility, compatibility with variable RES-E generation, comparing to other options [106]. In Tunisia, the model indicates the limited introduction of SOEC to support export-oriented targets, with significant high efficiency. The model's cost-optimized results (S5) that Tunisia and Morocco may need 36 % and 55 % less capacity than NHS projections (S1), while Algeria's requires an additional 2 GW of PEM capacity to meet its export targets. This reflects differences in national assumptions regarding technology efficiency.

Electricity and hydrogen production patterns in the Maghreb reflect

each country's RES-E integration and strategic focus Fig. 9. Tunisia and Morocco follow similar paths, expanding RES-E to support both domestic use and green hydrogen exports, while Algeria relies on blue hydrogen domestically and reserves green hydrogen for export. Total electricity generation scales with RES-E deployment, peaking under S4 where renewables power both electrolysis and desalination. By 2050, RES-E contributes 80 % of electricity in Tunisia and Morocco, compared to 27 % in Algeria, which maintains fossil fuel reliance.

6.6. Intra-regional trade

6.6.1. Electricity

Intra-regional electricity trade plays a key role in optimizing energy costs across The Maghreb. Tunisia consistently under both strategies, local only and local plus export, exports electricity to Algeria, utilizing 100 % of the assumed trade capacity (31 PJ), Tables 10 and 11. Under local-only strategies, Algeria becomes a net importer, sourcing from both Tunisia and Morocco, aligning with its reliance on blue hydrogen and limited RES-E expansion. In contrast, Morocco and Tunisia, driven by domestic green hydrogen targets (144 PJ and 269 PJ, respectively, by 2050), scale up renewables and emerge as regional electricity exporters.

However, when shifting to the local-plus-export strategy, a notable reversal in electricity trade patterns occurs between Algeria and Morocco. While Tunisia maintains its electricity exports to Algeria, Algeria itself transitions from an importer to an exporter, supplying electricity to Morocco. Morocco's much higher hydrogen export target (476 PJ) results in an increase in domestic electricity demand, making it more cost-effective to import electricity from Algeria (which has lower RES needs) rather than expanding its own grid-based generation at higher costs.

These results highlight a fundamental shift in regional energy interdependencies, where hydrogen production strategies also may reshape electricity trade patterns and cost structures. The ability of countries to leverage cross-border electricity trade as a flexibility mechanism will play a critical role in ensuring cost-optimal energy transitions while minimizing infrastructure expansion costs.

The results highlight a structural trade-off in RES-E allocation under the export-oriented strategy, where nearly all available renewables are directed toward electrolysis. RES-E dedicated to hydrogen production reaches 99 % in Tunisia, 93 % in Morocco, and 71 % in Algeria, a sharp increase from the local-only strategy (67 %, 40 %, and 0.6 %, respectively) Fig. 10. This shift is a direct consequence of the imposed hydrogen export targets, which drive the model to prioritize cost-effective hydrogen production over broader electricity sector integration. A key outcome is the reallocation of total electricity generation. Under the local-only strategy, 45 % of electricity in Tunisia, 65 % in Morocco, and 99 % in Algeria serves domestic demand, while hydrogen production remains secondary. With export-oriented hydrogen, 80 % of

Fig. 10. Share of renewable electricity consumption for hydrogen production under local and export-oriented strategies.

Fig. 11. Electricity Consumption Distribution: National Demand vs. Hydrogen Production Across Modelled Strategies.

Fig. 12. Impact of pipeline repurposing costs on intra-regional hydrogen trade flows.

Tunisia’s electricity, 70 % of Morocco’s, and 20 % of Algeria’s is redirected to hydrogen, intensifying competition for renewables. This fragmented transition supports hydrogen cost-efficiency but delays power sector decarbonization. The dominance of fossil-based domestic electricity raises grid flexibility concerns, limiting RES-E availability for national use Fig. 11. Stronger policy frameworks are needed to ensure RES-E expansion serves both hydrogen competitiveness and domestic clean energy goals, avoiding a hydrogen export economy sustained by fossil-dependent grids.

6.6.2. Hydrogen

To assess to which extent intra-regional trade would emerge as a cost-effective solution for meeting local hydrogen demand, several transport technologies were considered, including blending in natural gas grid, repurposing of existing pipelines or dedicated hydrogen pipeline investment. However, the results indicate that the model does not prioritize hydrogen trading between the Maghreb countries, suggesting that self-sufficiency in hydrogen production remains the least-cost pathway under the given assumptions. This outcome can be attributed to several key factors inherent in the TIMES optimization framework. First, the cost-competitiveness of domestic production appears to outweigh the economic advantages of importing hydrogen from neighboring countries. If each country can meet its own hydrogen demand at a lower or comparable cost, the model naturally avoids trade to minimize system-wide expenditures.

In reality, hydrogen market dynamics are shaped by a complex set of factors, that may influence not just cost competitiveness, particularly subsidies, but also geopolitical strategies and other factors such as long-term trade agreements. International funding mechanisms, particularly EU-backed hydrogen corridors, could alter the cost dynamics and make

cross-border hydrogen trade more attractive. The results Fig. 12 indicate that as intra-regional hydrogen transport costs decrease, the system gradually shifts from exclusive self-sufficiency to limited intra-regional hydrogen trade. Among the three-transport options pipeline repurposing is the most cost-effective solution for enabling hydrogen trade within the Maghreb region. This preference is driven by its lower capital costs compared to the high investment requirements of new dedicated hydrogen pipelines, as well as by blending limits for H2, which limits the amount of hydrogen in the transport network.

At an assumed cost of 0.5 Million euro per km [57], the model did not prioritize intra-regional hydrogen trade, instead favoring self-sufficiency, where each country produced its hydrogen domestically. To assess the cost threshold at which pipeline repurposing becomes competitive, a sensitivity analysis was conducted by gradually reducing repurposing costs. results reveal that hydrogen exports from Morocco to Tunisia via Algeria emerge only when repurposing costs decrease by approximately 80 %, reaching 0.1 million euro per km Fig. 12.

Despite this significant cost reduction, the volume of traded hydrogen is still limited, with imports into Tunisia reaching only 0.5 PJ (0.2 % of Tunisia’s local hydrogen demand). This limited trade results in approximately 10 million euro of hydrogen export revenues for Morocco, demonstrating that while lower transport costs make trade feasible, domestic hydrogen production remains the dominant supply pathway. This analysis underscores the critical role of transport infrastructure costs in determining the feasibility of regional hydrogen trade. While pipeline repurposing proves to be the most cost-effective transport option compared to blending and new pipeline construction, its competitiveness remains highly sensitive to capital costs. The results suggest that without external drivers such as government-led initiatives,

subsidies, or strategic hydrogen corridors, the Maghreb region may continue developing isolated hydrogen markets, rather than a coordinated regional hydrogen economy.

7. Conclusion

The Maghreb region has strong potential for green hydrogen production, enabled by abundant solar and wind resources. This study applies the TIMES-MAGE model to assess techno-economic trade-offs in Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria across five scenarios, comparing local-only and export-oriented strategies. Large-scale hydrogen deployment substantially increases RES-E demand, with investment needs doubling under export strategies. Green hydrogen exports may generate up to 90 billion Euro in revenues by 2050. If reinvested, these gains could stimulate growth and employment, though governance will determine their distributional impact. For local supply, RES-E electrolysis with grid-powered desalination is the most cost-effective option (2.3 €/kg H₂). Costs decrease further (2.01 €/kg) when using surface water, although this option is unsustainable due to water scarcity. In contrast, for export-oriented strategies, the lowest hydrogen production cost is 8.4 €/kg H₂, achieved through fully RES-powered electrolysis and desalination. Flexibility in energy sourcing slightly reduces costs, favoring mixed grid-RES configurations.

Meeting RES-E and hydrogen targets may require the full deployment of Tunisia's and Morocco's solar PV and wind capacity (~230 GW), prompting CSP expansion. Export strategies also raise electricity costs, particularly in Tunisia and Morocco. If export revenues are not reinvested to offset these increased costs, there is a potential risk that exports could hinder a fair energy transition. Hydrogen production for exportation triples water use, adding pressure to already scarce water resources. Although representing a small share of national reserves, it competes with agriculture and domestic use, reinforcing the need for integrated water-energy planning.

National strategies diverge: Tunisia pursues aggressive exports, requiring policy and financial support; Morocco adopts a balanced path; Algeria follows a conservative route with limited green hydrogen deployment. Export scenarios shift nearly all RES-E to hydrogen, risking domestic decarbonization delays. Intra-regional hydrogen trade remains less cost-effective than domestic supply, though pipeline repurposing, if costs fall fivefold, could enable limited trade.

Limitations of this study include the simplified representation of infrastructure and the exclusion of political and market dynamics. Electricity demand projections were defined exogenously based on national planning documents rather than being derived endogenously within the model. While this ensures alignment with official energy strategies and sectoral targets, it limits the model's ability to reflect demand-side responses to changing policies, price signals, or structural transformations. The analysis also focuses solely on the power sector, given its central role in hydrogen production and desalination. As such, it does not capture interactions with other sectors such as transport, industry, or heating, which are important for a comprehensive energy systems perspective. Additionally, the model applies a temporal resolution of 48 time slices, to balance computational feasibility with the need to reflect seasonal and diurnal variation. Although suitable for long-term strategic planning, this resolution constrains the model's ability to capture short-term operational dynamics and flexibility requirements. Future research should aim to endogenize demand modeling, increase temporal granularity, incorporate biomass-based hydrogen production, include derivative fuels such as ammonia or methanol, and explore non-conventional water sources such as treated wastewater to enhance both realism and sustainability.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yasmine Ayed: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization,

Resources, Formal analysis. **Patrícia Fortes:** Visualization, Software, Methodology, Validation, Resources, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Rafat Al Afif:** Validation, Supervision.

8. Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT and Grammarly in order to improve readability, check grammar and spelling. After using these tools/services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT I.P) for funding Yasmine Ayed [UI/BD/150894/2021], CENSE (UIDB/04085/2020 - 10.54499/UIDB/04085/2020, UIDP/04085/2020 - 10.54499/UIDP/04085/2020) and CHANGE (10.54499/LA/P/0121/2020). This work was also supported by the H2tALENT project (10.3030/101137611, GA 101137611).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.150193>.

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